

A Trek on the Non-homogeneous Quaternary Octic Surface

$$x^3 + y^3 = 8zw^7$$

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Abstract

The main aim of this paper is to illustrate the process of obtaining non-zero distinct integer solutions to the non-homogeneous quaternary octic equation given by $x^3 + y^3 = 8zw^7$. Substitution technique and factorization method are utilized to obtain the same. We are able to solve the given octic equation through the methods suggested above for obtaining plenty of non-zero distinct integer solutions.

Keywords: Non-homogeneous equation, Octic equation, Quaternary octic equation, Integer Solutions

Introduction

The theory of Diophantine equations offers a rich variety of fascinating problems. In particular, homogeneous and non-homogeneous equations of higher degree have aroused the interest of many mathematicians since antiquity. For example, in [1-5], the authors are analysed cubic equations with multiple variables. In [6, 7], the quartic and quintic equations have been considered for obtaining many integer solutions. In [8-10], the sixth degree equations with multiple variables have been discussed for various choices of integer solutions. In [11], an octic equation has been presented with different sets of integer solutions. In [12], a ninth degree equation with three unknowns has been studied for finding its solutions in integers. In [13,14], polynomial equations of degree ten with six unknowns have been searched for determining their integer solutions. The above problems motivated us to get integer solutions for another interesting eighth degree equation with four unknowns given by

$x^3 + y^3 = 8zw^7$. Substitution technique and factorization method are utilized to determine the same.

Method of analysis

The non-homogeneous polynomial equation of degree eight with four unknowns under consideration is given by

$$x^3 + y^3 = 8zw^7 \tag{1}$$

The insertion of the transformation

$$x = u + v, y = u - v, z = u, u \neq v \neq 0 \tag{2}$$

in (1) leads to the non-homogeneous ternary heptic equation

$$u^2 + 3v^2 = 4w^7 \tag{3}$$

To start with, it is seen after some algebra that (3) is satisfied by

$$u = 2r(r^2 + 3s^2)^3, v = 2s(r^2 + 3s^2)^3, w = (r^2 + 3s^2)$$

and from (2), the corresponding values of x, y, z satisfying (1) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 2(r + s)(r^2 + 3s^2)^3 \\ y &= 2(r - s)(r^2 + 3s^2)^3 \\ z &= 2r(r^2 + 3s^2)^3, r \neq s \neq 0 \end{aligned}$$

The process of obtaining varieties of integer solutions to (1) through solving (3) is presented below:

Process 1

The choice

$$v = kw^3 \tag{4}$$

in (3) gives

$$u^2 = w^6(4w - 3k^2) \tag{5}$$

The expression $(4w - 3k^2)$ is a perfect square when

$$w = (s^2 - s + 1)k^2 \tag{6}$$

and from (5) & (4), one has

$$\begin{aligned} u &= k^7(s^2 - s + 1)^3(2s - 1) \\ v &= k^7(s^2 - s + 1)^3 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Substituting (7) in (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} x &= k^7(s^2 - s + 1)^3(2s) \\ y &= k^7(s^2 - s + 1)^3(2s - 2) \\ z &= k^7(s^2 - s + 1)^3(2s - 1) \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Thus, (6) & (8) satisfy (1).

Process 2

The choice

$$v = 2k w^3 \quad (9)$$

in (3) gives

$$u^2 = 4w^6 (w - 3k^2) \quad (10)$$

The expression $(w - 3k^2)$ is a perfect square when

$$w = (s^2 + 3)k^2 \quad (11)$$

and from (10) & (9),one has

$$\begin{aligned} u &= 2k^7 (s^2 + 3)^3 (s) \\ v &= 2k^7 (s^2 + 3)^3 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Substituting (12) in (2),we get

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 2k^7 (s^2 + 3)^3 (s + 1) \\ y &= 2k^7 (s^2 + 3)^3 (s - 1) \\ z &= 2k^7 (s^2 + 3)^3 (s) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Thus,(11) & (13) satisfy (1).

Note 1**Process 3**

The choice

$$u = k w^3 \quad (14)$$

in (3) gives

$$3v^2 = w^6 (4w - k^2) \quad (15)$$

The expression $(4w - k^2)$ is a perfect square multiple of three when

$$w = (3s^2 - 3s + 1)k^2 \quad (16)$$

and from (15) & (14),one has

$$\begin{aligned} v &= k^7 (3s^2 - 3s + 1)^3 (2s - 1) \\ u &= k^7 (3s^2 - 3s + 1)^3 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Substituting (17) in (2),we get

$$\begin{aligned} x &= k^7 (3s^2 - 3s + 1)^3 (2s) \\ y &= k^7 (3s^2 - 3s + 1)^3 (2 - 2s) \\ z &= k^7 (3s^2 - 3s + 1)^3 \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Thus,(16) & (18) satisfy (1).

Process 4

The choice

$$u = 2k w^3 \tag{19}$$

in (3) gives

$$3v^2 = 4w^6 (w - k^2) \tag{20}$$

The expression $(w - k^2)$ is a perfect square multiple of three when

$$w = (3s^2 + 1)k^2 \tag{21}$$

and from (20) & (19), one has

$$\begin{aligned} v &= 2k^7 (3s^2 + 1)^3 (s) \\ u &= 2k^7 (3s^2 + 1)^3 \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Substituting (22) in (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 2k^7 (3s^2 + 1)^3 (1 + s) \\ y &= 2k^7 (3s^2 + 1)^3 (1 - s) \\ z &= 2k^7 (3s^2 + 1)^3 \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

Thus, (21) & (23) satisfy (1).

Process 5

Let

$$w = a^2 + 3b^2 \tag{24}$$

Consider the integer 4 on the R.H.S. of (3) as

$$4 = (1 + i\sqrt{3})(1 - i\sqrt{3}) \tag{25}$$

Substitute (24) & (25) in (3) and employ the method of factorization. On equating the positive factors on both sides, one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} u + i\sqrt{3}v &= (1 + i\sqrt{3})(a + i\sqrt{3}b)^7 \\ &= (1 + i\sqrt{3})[f(a, b) + i\sqrt{3}g(a, b)] \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} f(a, b) &= a^7 - 63a^5b^2 + 315a^3b^4 - 189ab^6 \\ g(a, b) &= 7a^6b - 105a^4b^3 + 189a^2b^5 - 27b^7 \end{aligned}$$

On equating the coefficients of corresponding terms in (26), one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} u &= f(a, b) - 3g(a, b) \\ v &= f(a, b) + g(a, b) \end{aligned}$$

In view of (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 2f(a, b) - 2g(a, b) \\ y &= -4g(a, b) \\ z &= f(a, b) - 3g(a, b) \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

Thus, (24) & (27) satisfy (1).

Process 6

Write (3) as

$$u^2 + 3v^2 = 4w^7 * 1 \quad (28)$$

Consider the integer 1 on the R.H.S. of (28) as

$$1 = \frac{(1+i\sqrt{3})(1-i\sqrt{3})}{4} \quad (29)$$

Substitute (24),(25) & (29) in (28) and employ the method of factorization. On equating the positive factors on both sides ,one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} u + i\sqrt{3}v &= (1+i\sqrt{3})[f(a,b) + i\sqrt{3}g(a,b)] \frac{(1+i\sqrt{3})}{2} \\ &= (-1+i\sqrt{3})[f(a,b) + i\sqrt{3}g(a,b)] \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

On equating the coefficients of corresponding terms in (30) ,one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} u &= -f(a,b) - 3g(a,b) \\ v &= f(a,b) - g(a,b) \end{aligned}$$

In view of (2),we have

$$\begin{aligned} x &= -4g(a,b) \\ y &= -2f(a,b) - 2g(a,b) \\ z &= -f(a,b) - 3g(a,b) \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Thus, (24) & (31) satisfy (1).

Note 1

In addition to (29), the integer 1 has the following representations:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= \frac{(r^2 - 3s^2 + i\sqrt{3}(2rs))(r^2 - 3s^2 - i\sqrt{3}(2rs))}{(r^2 + 3s^2)^2} \\ 1 &= \frac{(3r^2 - s^2 + i\sqrt{3}(2rs))(3r^2 - s^2 - i\sqrt{3}(2rs))}{(3r^2 + s^2)^2} \\ 1 &= \frac{(6s^2 - 6s + 1 + i\sqrt{3}(2s-1))(6s^2 - 6s + 1 - i\sqrt{3}(2s-1))}{(6s^2 - 6s + 2)^2} \\ 1 &= \frac{(2s^2 - 2s - 1 + i\sqrt{3}(2s-1))(2s^2 - 2s - 1 - i\sqrt{3}(2s-1))}{(2s^2 - 2s + 2)^2} \end{aligned}$$

Repeating the above process, one obtains four more sets of integer solutions to (1).

Conclusion

In this paper, an attempt has been made to obtain many integer solutions to non-homogeneous Diophantine equation of degree eight with four unknowns. Substitution strategy and factorization technique are utilized for finding the required integer solutions to the eighth degree equation with four unknowns. In this analysis, the given equation is reduced to lower degree equation for which the integer solutions can be found elegantly.

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